

GENERATING POSITIVE EMOTIONS DURING DRIVING

THE PRODUCT QUALITIES OF A CAR AFFECT EMOTIONAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Our lives depend on mobility, and we spend much of our precious time undertaking transportation activities during our daily routines. Generally, these activities may seem like a waste of time and turn out to be self-torture. What's more, being a passenger is somehow more advantageous than being a driver, because drivers have to concentrate only on the activity of driving. Since traffic involves unexpected and unfortunate events, this stressful environment generates negative feelings. From this point of view, driving seems to be an activity generating more negative feelings than positive ones. In this framework, this study aims to find out cues about driving activity and design solutions which generate positive effects by identifying the underlying reasons and expectations of the users with regard to product qualities.

KEYWORDS: *subjective well-being, transportation technologies, positive emotions*

INTRODUCTION

Transportation is one of the major activities of our lives. Everyday we use several different transportation modes to reach our aimed destinations. It is possible to define transportation in two different ways according to the aim of the activity, one is transportation for work and the other is transportation for leisure. According to research carried out for investigating transportation modes affecting the happiness level of users, using personal cars is still the most popular way of transportation for work, even though negative emotions are mostly experienced during transportation to work, by driving personal cars (Duarte et al., 2009).

As technology enables higher speeds, travelling distances increase and the average time spent during transportation for work averages at about one hour a day per person (Lyons and Urry, 2005). It is possible to say that the time spent in transportation is a significant amount our lives. During our transportation activities due to misfortunate, unexpected events such as congested roads, accidents, violations, and so on, sometimes it is impossible to adjust timing and to keep calm in traffic. Moreover, the driving activity is much more stressful since it necessitates personal control and attention over the events happening around you.

There are several in-vehicle technologies designed to enhance our experience within the car, since we spend an important amount of our time during driving. These technologies become a way to cope with stress caused by outer effects by assisting or even sometimes taking the control from us. Even though these applications aim to reduce stress, they generally focus on safety related problems. Furthermore, staying away from stress is not only related with support and safety, but also positively affected by personal wellbeing. Therefore, it is important to consider possible design solutions to enhance wellbeing rather than minimizing problems and enhancing safety, which needs a possibility driven design approach rather than problem driven solutions.

In relation to these arguments, this study aims to understand the relationship between subjective well-being and in-vehicle technologies, and to find ways to create positive emotions for drivers during the activity of transportation for work. In order to reach the aim, the following questions are to be answered:

- What are the product qualities of their cars that generate positive emotions during the activity of transportation to work for drivers?
- What are the expectations, expected product qualities, of drivers from their cars in the future in order to create positive emotions?

In order to gain answers, it is crucial to consult the literature and research available on transportation and positive psychology.

TRANSPORTATION AND POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY

Scanning through transportation and positive psychology research, it is possible to identify the main research focuses, which are: stress and time relationship, urban planning, and transportation mode choice. There are studies focusing on the statistics about transportation activities from economy literature, generally focusing on the time spent and its economic results, and which shows that an average person spends about an hour per day in transportation activities (Schafer & Victor, 2000; Lyons & Urry, 2005). From an urban planning point of view:

- Reports focusing on the growing population, polarization of economic growth, rise in greenhouse gases, and decreasing transportation budgets (Falconer & Mitchell, 2012) are suggesting solutions about transportation infrastructure of a city, including intelligent communication agents.
- Studies like Schroeter & Rakotonirainy (2012) focus on the urban informatics systems and their benefits to safety by organizing an idea creation workshop with the help of fourteen Urban Informatics research experts. These workshops focus on 'enhancing social interaction between people in urban environments' (Schoeter & Rakotonirainy, 2012, p.1.), and providing this ergonomically and safely.
- Papers asking the question about the meaning of electric vehicles among people and investigating EVs through performance, interest, and meaning perceived by drivers and others (Burgess et al., 2013). Also another study is investigating if EVs have any effects on driving behaviors and encourage sustainable behaviors (Labeye et al., 2012).

At the same time there are studies about intelligent in-vehicle systems from different scopes like acceptability, adaptability, driver behavior, behavior adaptation, driver attitudes, primary and secondary tasks of driving, information load... etc.

- Bader et al., (2011) discuss if the drivers accept recommendations about later actions (proactive) while driving. A scenario has been built about gas station recommenders; selecting gas stations according to user preferences and this in-vehicle system used by fifteen volunteers and then evaluated by using TAM of Davis (1989).
- Kujala's (2009) study is about the effects of two user interface menu structures compared in a driving simulation with the measures of visual time-sharing efficiency, visual load, driving performance, and secondary task performance.
- Acceptability of ITS systems is also a question for many papers (Regan et al., 2002; Vlassenroot et al., 2010), but these papers generally focus on some of the ITS technologies, and these kind of studies are usually conducted with psychologists and engineers in cooperation.

Looking through the researches above, it is possible to see that there are studies mainly focusing on the transportation systems from a problem solving point of view. As was mentioned before, creating a more positive traffic environment can be achieved by focusing on the driver within the driving to work context. To define and understand the positive effect psychology, literature and the well-being concepts are important sources. In the following part well-being and positive effect will be defined.

What is Well-being

Well-being is a concept that is defined in several different ways, sometimes depending on personal happiness, others, seeking positive effects. It also used to be defined as the absence of suffering, but today it is much more like the relationship between positive effects and negative effects.

There are two different approaches to the concept of well-being. Forgeard et al. (2011) describes these approaches:

- Objective measures of well-being; that has objective criteria generally based on needs
- Subjective measures of well-being; not consisting of a list about needs but focusing on the individual's own conative states.

Objective well-being depends on the concept of well-being in an objective way apart from a person's own thoughts about his/her life, whereas subjective well-being depends on the person's own thoughts about his/her life. Since the study focuses on the concept of well-being at a personal level, subjective well-being will be the main focus of the study.

Subjective well-being can be summarized as 'people's cognitive and affective evaluations of their lives' (Diener, 2000, p. 34). It depends on the people's own evaluations about how their lives are. As was mentioned before, Diener (2000) also focuses on the balance between negative and positive effects in a person's life. For example, more pleasant and few unpleasant emotions, engaging activities, gives satisfaction to a person with relation to his/her life. From Diener et al.'s (1999) point of view, it is possible to identify the components of subjective well-being as;

- Pleasant Effect; joy, elation, contentment/pride, affection, happiness, ecstasy
- Unpleasant Effect; guilt and shame, sadness, anxiety and worry/anger, stress, depression, envy
- Life Satisfaction; desire to change life, satisfaction with current life, satisfaction with past, satisfaction with future, significant others' views of one's life
- Domain Satisfaction; work, family, leisure, health, finances, self, one's group (Diener et al., 1999, p.277).

During the research, the general focus point will be the pleasant effect component of subjective well-being.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study is to find out product qualities of a car generating positive feelings amongst drivers. In order to find out answers:

- The first step is to identify a suitable user group; the second step is to gather the demographic information of the user group; and, lastly a semi-structured interview has been conducted among suitable user groups with the help of visual materials that I prepared to stimulate emotions and experiences.

Selection of user group

The user group is identified as:

- Car owners; since the ownership has effect on subjective well-being.
- As the research focuses on the activity of transportation for work the user group will be chosen among the people who drive to and from work in their daily routine.
- The age group is identified as between 30-50 year olds; people who generally have a consistent daily routine.
- Gender is kept in equal numbers.

The interviews are carried out with eighteen users, the initial information is consisting of mostly demographic questions like;

- Age (ranged from 29-49, with a mean of $M=36,6$)
- Gender (kept equal: 9 females, 9 males)

- The average duration of the journey between home and work (ranged from 8 to 15 without traffic but rises to 45 minutes according to traffic conditions).

Interview Structure

For the last step an interview is conducted with laddering techniques. Before the interview, people are shown two mood boards that display pictures of drivers feeling positive and negative effects. These mood boards are prepared for stimulating positive and negative effects, as well as ideas and past experiences on the respondents.

- Boards are created with an online image search using the keywords obtained from Diener et al.'s (1999) Components of Subjective Well-being table, under the pleasant and unpleasant effects titles.
- Keywords; angry driver, anxious driver, contented driver, depressed driver, elated driver, envious, feeling ecstasy, feeling shame, guilty driver, happy driver, joyful driver, positive driving, proud driver, sad driver, stressful driver, worried driver. (Keywords are generally associated with the words driving or driver, but some of them were used with the word feeling, since there are no healthy images representing the feeling in a driving context.)
- In addition to images, also those keywords are used in the mood boards to clarify the exact (intended) feelings and to keep users engaged with the images more than just for a glimpse while reading the words.
- Firstly the negative emotion board has been given to the respondent.

Figure 1. Negative feelings mood board

Figure 2. Positive feelings mood board

The user is asked to look at the mood board and imagine his/her journey of the day, and then the mood board is taken away.

- Secondly the positive emotions board is given to the respondent and left in front of him/her during the interview to stimulate positive feelings.

After that point, with the help of mood boards, the interview is conducted. Since it is possible to analyze the driving experience in three phases, the interview is carried out in an activity based manner.

Figure 3. Phases of driving activity

The interview is built upon the scenario of the user's journey between home and work. To keep the time line in its normal positions, the morning journey experience to work is the first event, and the last the evening experience of returning home. The following questions are asked about the three driving phases:

- What do you experience that makes you feel much more positive while you are walking to your car/ driving your car to/from work/leaving your car behind after your journey?

- How positive do they make you feel? Why?
- Which features do you expect from your car that affect you positively?
- What else could be useful which is not available right now but may be used in the future?

RESULTS

This study has been conducted with 18 participants; aged between 29-49 with a mean of $M=36,6$, distributed evenly in both genders, and consisting of car owners driving between their homes and work in their daily routines.

Users are interviewed with laddering techniques about their daily experiences driving between their homes and work, and are ultimately asked about the expectations they have from their cars in the future to generate a more positive environment during driving to and from work.

Data Coding

The data gained by the interviews are transcribed to an Excel sheet and the data was coded under four categories:

- Affected: the feelings that are affected by the product qualities of car. Feelings are keywords obtained from Diener et al.'s (1999) Components of Subjective Well-being table under the pleasant and unpleasant effects titles.

- Requirement: the basic requirement that affects the user
- Product quality: the requirements and design features engaged with the product and qualities.
- Design features: the features that the user already uses or wants to use.

ANALYSES

As a result of the coded data, there appears to be three major driver personas related with in-vehicle requirements. What is common for all personas is the desire for ‘comfort’ related requirements, as expected. However, the second group of preferences changes from persona to persona under three titles: safety, support, and aesthetics. One third of the users are driven by comfort and support, and are named as ‘moody drivers’; one sixth of the users are driven by comfort and safety, and are named as ‘cautious drivers’; lastly one sixth of the users are driven by comfort and aesthetics, and are named ‘image oriented drivers’. It is summarized in Figure 4 by listing

requirements according to percentages of mention times by different personas.

Even though the major requirements are the same and close to each other, the interpretation of concepts differ between these groups.

As can be seen from Figure 5, Moody drivers' interpretation of comfort mostly involves the qualities of smartness and personal space in a car. They need their cars to be ready before their access, to have information about the different situations such as tire condition, damage if there is any...etc. that would interrupt their driving routines. Also they want automatization for some routine driving activities such as changing gears, accelerating...etc.. They feel the need for support during their journey when they face an unexpected, unwanted event. They are also concerned mostly about the smartness of the car, so that it is able to understand the mood of the driver and possesses smart solutions for different situations. Their third requirement is about safety, which is mostly dependent again on the smartness of the car, suggesting and applying solutions for threats to the safety of the car, and also, again, automatization for some activities.

Figure 4. User classification according to percentages of mention times of major requirements

Figure 6 is about requirement relations of cautious drivers whose major requirements are comfort and safety. Similar to moody drivers, cautious drivers' comfort is highly dependent on the smartness and personal space of the car, but their major concerns are about gaining information and automatization of some driving activities. Secondly their needs for safety also depend on the smartness of the car which involves again some warning options and automatization. What's more, production quality is another concern about safety deriving from need for different materials and visual access solutions. Lastly cautious drivers have the need for support dependent on the smart options mostly involving assistance and mood management.

As with the last group, image oriented drivers are mostly affected by comfort options and also aesthetic properties of a car. Their expectations from comfort differ from other drivers as they mostly focus on the personal space of a car that they create away from traffic during their journey. Their second requirement is about aesthetics, which is dependent on the appearance and image of the car; from color to license plate they personalize their cars and feel affection about some aesthetic properties of it. Lastly they also need support during their journey and assistance with their personal needs. Figure 7 summarizes the requirement relations of image-oriented drivers.

As can be seen from the figures, there are some similarities and differences between three groups of drivers with regards to requirements and also their interpretations of these requirements. In order to understand these properties deeper the sub requirements of the users are analyzed.

Comfort related qualities

Comfort is the most mentioned requirement by all the groups, but it refers to different kinds of needs and wants. It is mostly dependent on the qualities of smartness and personal space. Figure 8 summarizes the difference between the user group about smartness and the personal space of the car.

For smartness of the car, moody and image-oriented drivers generally want their cars to be ready before their access, organizing the in-car climate conditions and air quality. They want to enter a cozy environment with personalized settings which has an organized climate through the air and the places that they touch. Also the first impression of the car was built with an indoor smell, which evokes the feelings of an unhealthy, plastic, dirty environment, especially after sun exposure. Furthermore cautious drivers mostly focus on the information they gain about the route suggestions and organize their daily schedule around that information. Moody drivers need information not only about their daily schedule but also information about parking spots and possible bad surprises, like broken car functions that may slow them down and waste their time. Lastly all groups of drivers want smartness automatization, but for different reasons cautious drivers need automation of driving activities for safer environments, whereas moody and image-oriented drivers want it for getting rid of boredom and tiredness caused by the routine of driving activities during traffic.

Figure 6. Requirement relations of cautious drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 5. Requirement relations of moody drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 7. Requirement relations of image oriented drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 8. Comfort related product qualities(according to the percentages of mention times)

Personal space of the car is another factor that affects mostly the moody and image oriented drivers and that is mostly about the cozy environment that they create during their journey, like having coffee around with the company of music and an ergonomic, relaxing, even massaging seating options. Furthermore, image-oriented drivers are oriented by their images too and need extra storage areas inside for their personal belongings, like sunglasses, wallets and spare shoes. Moreover

moody and image-oriented drivers both focus on the ease of use of the controls with understandable interfaces inside the car, but image-oriented drivers also ask for playful interactions with these controls through tactual properties during driving. Lastly cautious drivers have the need for a cozy environment, but they prefer to stay low and don't want to be distracted by these properties.

Support related qualities

Apart from comfort, overall support is the second most mentioned requirement. There are also several similar and different tendencies involved with support related product qualities that are summarized in Figure 9.

Support related qualities are highly affected by the smartness of the car. Moody drivers are the ones that need support after comfort, and they highly need mood management in cases of an unexpected, unwanted event. For moody drivers mood management depends mostly on the in-car air conditioning. When they need to cool down they actually need in-car temperature to be slightly cooler, and they also ask for the in-car air to become fresher; refreshing them and giving them the feeling of nature that could take them away from that moment. Music is important for moody and image-oriented drivers who want the smartness to understand their moods and organize

a different musical experience to revitalize or to support their mood for the day. Communication with other cars is important for moody and cautious drivers who want to express their feelings with more creative ways than claxons, which are subtle. Claxons are used for a number of different expressions, such as: thanking, anger, warning...etc.; in a mixed environment it is not easy to determine why and to whom that expression is for. This causes more stress and misunderstandings that bring the need for to-the-point and clear communication options. Assistance is also about the smartness of the car, which is needed by all the driver groups. During parking all groups need assistance for precision; to park according to comfort of the near cars, distance needed to open the doors and pedestrian comfort. Also moody and image-oriented drivers are not as careful as cautious drivers about safety precautions, so they also need assistance for the forgotten valuables, and for locking the car while leaving.

Figure 9. Support related product qualities (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 10. Safety related product qualities(according to the percentages of mention times)

Apart from mood management and assistance, connectivity is a major element of the smartness. Connectivity is mostly about the personal devices for moody drivers to socialize and to have the company of their friends during their journey, to complete necessary work related things, to get rid of the stress that they have, and lastly, generally during the evening journey and similarly to image-oriented drivers, to plan and organize activities from cooking and food ordering, to social activities and meeting points during their journey, as well as the ability to update their destinations. Besides, cautious drivers are mostly focusing on a wider online system to be part of legal actions about rude, dangerous drivers, and recording during driving to share with legal forces. Moody and image-oriented drivers also want

to be part of the legal actions, but moreover they want to be aware of route updates and whole traffic systems.

Safety related qualities

The third most mentioned quality is safety, which is again related with smartness and also production quality of the car. Cautious drivers are mostly focusing on the safety related qualities and the relations are summarized in Figure 10.

Cautious drivers want to be warned about outer effects during driving since as well as inner distractions, like music, there are also outer distraction, like noise, claxons...etc. They have a need to be aware of the outer events but also they don't want

to be interrupted by too many noises and the smells from traffic, so they close their windows for some isolation. In that case they want their cars to be aware and warn them about outer events, close drivers, emergency vehicles...etc. Also they feel anxiety about the safety of their cars out of their sights, which is shared by moody and image-oriented drivers too. The alarm options are no solution for their anxiety because sometimes it is not possible to hear these sounds. Also the intruder runs away when the alarm rings, which makes it impossible to catch them. They need a more personalized system that reaches to their communication devices; or even the key of the car can be an alarm option. Automatization is also mentioned during comfort options, since the drivers want to leave the control to the car and relax in case of safety, fatigue, or even boredom. From a safety point of view, the way the users want automatization changes from driver to driver. Moody drivers do not want the automatization to interrupt their driving flows; they need it to be subtle and invisible. At the same time, like cautious drivers, they want automatization to be couching, supporting learning processes for new starters and decision making in case of an inevitable accident that distracts and stresses the driver and affects the decision making process.

Lastly, the production quality is engaged with safety options, with cautious drivers mostly focusing on the visual access options of their cars. As climate changes cause distortions in visual access they ask for a easy cleaning, self cleaning material that won't distract them during their journey with visual access areas like mirrors and glass areas. Also, the durability of the materials in case of an unwanted incident evokes trust in all of the driver groups towards their cars, which bring them contentment and pride.

Apart from these qualities, aesthetics is highly important for image driven drivers. They want to feel special with certain qualities of their cars. Aesthetics is mostly related with the appearance and image of the car, which is affected by an intimidating look created by a higher and aggressive design of the car. They also look for a unique color that is not easy to find, or the color used in the commercials while launching a new model. Another important requirement is also about self-cleaning materials; apart from safety it is mostly about the appearance of the car. Image-oriented drivers feel pride and happiness while approaching their cars and they want to see a cleaner outlook. Moreover, when they reach their cars they want to touch cleaner surfaces designed in a way that is not affected by the outer effects. Lastly some of the drivers mentioned the possibility of personalizing license plates with letters and numbers. They have a need for personalization options, such as license plates or a unique color, which can be a clue for design solutions involving personalization options.

DISCUSSION

There are several requirements that are mentioned during the study by the drivers. As can be expected, comfort is the most mentioned requirement for feeling positive effects, but there

are three different tendencies that the study revealed according to the mention times of the second major requirement, and the drivers grouped under three groups such as moody, image-oriented, and cautious drivers.

Scanning through the product qualities related with the requirements of all groups the major factor can be identified as the smartness that is related with nearly all the requirements. As the technology develops day by day, it also gets into every corner of our lives, maintaining our comfort and supporting us. Also the driving experience becomes richer with the technological developments and smart applications day by day. As a result the expectations of the drivers depend more on the smart options. Moreover, as the communication devices become mobile, they become our main companion in every aspect of our lives. Therefore connectivity creates a higher demand. In this study this is mostly about personal devices but for the future connectivity will become crucial for designing a whole transportation system that is aware of every other device around.

Apart from smartness, drivers have a need for creating an in-car environment away from traffic, which is highly related with the personal space of the car, which used to be defined as the interior design of the car, but nowadays is more dependent on the technological advances that support the comfort of the drivers. That also involves smartness in a way that realizes the driver's condition and offers personalized options for different drivers; like massaging and adapting seating and playful driving activities. Even the musical experience involves technological advances around personalization and sound quality.

Also, the production quality of the car is highly engaged with the safety precautions, and is again dependent on the technological advances about materials that in a way involve smartness, like self-cleaning or adjusting according to external effects. Durability of the materials also evokes trust in the car, and enables drivers to feel pride and contentment.

Lastly, the study reveals the close relationship between comfort, support, safety, aesthetic options, and feeling positive, but also shows the close relationship between requirements and technological advances. All of these requirements are musts, but the importance levels change according to user groups.

FURTHER STUDIES

The study revealed three groups of users distinguished from each other according to their main requirements for feeling positive effect in the driving context. There are some similarities and differences between the product qualities they associate with their requirements. Moreover there are some similarities and differences while interpreting product qualities, but their most important common point is technological advances and the concept of smartness. The study revealed that the requirements of the drivers mostly depended on technological advances, and even though it is interpreted differently, the smartness of the car from different points of view.

For further studies the relationship between technology and requirements will be interpreted through the identification of user and technology relationship.

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